

LIGHT DISTRIBUTION AND GLARE PREVENTION PERFORMANCE OF A COMPLEX FENESTRATION SYSTEM: A SIMULATION BASED EVALUATION

Paulína Šujanová¹, Jozef Hraška²

¹ Department of Building Structures, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Radlinského 11, 813 68 Bratislava, Slovakia, Email: paulina.sujanova@stuba.sk

² Department of Building Structures, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Radlinského 11, 813 68 Bratislava, Slovakia, Email: jozef.hraska@stuba.sk

ABSTRACT

In this paper, performance evaluation of a complex fenestration system is presented, using Radiance based computer simulation. This is done on an office model space with integrated double transparent facade, with complex geometry of each facade layer. To evaluate the ability of the CFS to distribute the light in the interior space and to prevent glare, illuminance distribution in the office space has been calculated for three critical days: (1) March 21 st – equinox, at 12:00 PM which for 48° latitude corresponds to sun elevation angle of approximately 40°; (2) June 21 st – summer solstice, at 12:00 PM which corresponds to sun elevation angle of approximately 63°; December 21 st – winter solstice, at 12:00 PM which corresponds to sun elevation angle of approximately 17°. This was done for three states of the CFS: (a) facade model with no blinds applied; (b) facade model with blinds applied with 0° slat tilt; (c) facade model with blinds applied with 45° slat tilt. The results are drawn in regards to the requirements of the draft standard prEN 17037 Daylight in buildings.

GLARE

Glare in general is defined by IESNA as “the sensation produced by luminance within the visual field that is sufficiently greater than the luminance to which the eyes are adapted to cause annoyance, discomfort or loss in visual performance and visibility” [1.], whereas CIE defines glare as “a condition of vision in which there is discomfort or a reduction in the ability to see details or object, caused by an unsuitable distribution or range of luminance, or by extreme contrasts” [2.]. To reduce the risk of glare occurrence the use of shading devices is recommended in all spaces with daylight openings [3.].

The Daylight Glare Probability (*DGP*) is recommended to use to assess the protections from glare for spaces where activities are similar to reading and writing according prEN 17037 [3.].

$$DGP = 5.87 \times 10^{-5} \times E_v + 9.18 \times 10^{-2} \times \log \left(1 + \sum_i \frac{L_{s,i}^2 \times \omega_{s,i}}{E_v^{1.87} \times P_i^2} \right) + 0.16 \quad (1)$$

where E_v is the illuminance at the eye level in lux, measured perpendicular to the line of sight; L_s is the luminance of the glare source in cd/m^2 ; P is the position index describing the angular displacement of the glare source from the occupant’s line of sight; ω_s is the solid angle subtended by the glare source; and i is the number of glare source. For evaluation of glare probability, in rooms with multiple possible position and activities, the worst case scenario should be evaluated and fulfill the glare criteria. To ensure glare protection the use of

shading devices for all daylight openings is recommended. The categorization of DGP value ranges can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1 Categorization of DGP value ranges according prEN 17037

Criterion	DGP
Glare is mostly not-perceived	$DGP \leq 0.35$
Glare is perceived but mostly not disturbing	$0.35 < DGP \leq 0.40$
Glare is perceived and often disturbing	$0.4 < DGP \leq 0.45$
Glare is perceived and mostly intolerable	$DGP > 0.45$

For annual evaluation a minimum recommendation is that the DGP_t value does not exceed a value of 0.45 in more than $f_{DGP, exceed} = 5\%$ of the occupation time of the evaluated space, whereas the occupation time t_{ref} is set as the time between 8h – 18h on Monday to Friday through the year (even though the real usage time might differ).

The temporal behavior of glare occurrence can be calculated as:

$$f_{DGP, exceed} = \frac{t_{glare}}{t_{ref}}, \quad (2)$$

where t_{glare} is the amount of time through the reference usage time t_{ref} when the DGP exceeds the threshold DGP_t . The draft standard further defines recommended levels of threshold for glare protection where $DGP_{e < 5\%}$ equal to:

- 0,45 represents the minimum level of glare protection;
- 0,40 represents the medium level of glare protection;
- 0,35 represents the high level of glare protection.

According the draft version of Daylight in buildings standard two methods can be used to verify the glare protection. To these belong:

1. A simplified method of verification of the shading device ability to provide adequate glare protection.
2. By on site measurements that enable calculation of DGP values.

However, the standard enables to use an annual DGP calculation as described above.

It has to be mentioned that the standard defines only glare protection evaluation methods based on measurements. Predictive methods based on simulation and not yet described. In this paper we will present on a model office with a complex fenestration system with integrated venetian blinds the simplified annual glare evaluation and a simulation based annual DGP calculation.

TEST OFFICE MODEL

Figure 1 Scheme of the simulation model

The location, office and facade design is based on standard design of the Southwest facing offices (34.2°meridian) at C building block of the Faculty of Civil Engineering of the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava. Standard interior dimensions of the office space are 2900 × 5700 × 2650 mm, Figure 1. The

reflectance of the surface reflectance was chosen according the recommendations of prEN 17037, with reflectance $\rho = 0.7$ for ceiling, $\rho = 0.5$ for walls, $\rho = 0.3$ for floor, and $\rho = 0.2$ for terrain.

Figure 2 Scheme of the double transparent facade

The daylight opening is a double transparent facade with a 180 mm wide ventilated gap with integrated venetian blinds, Figure 2. The exterior glazing is a float glass and the interior is composed out of insulating double glazing, with a normal-hemispherical light transmittance τ_{glazing} of 0.72, Table 2. The glazing frame is made of aluminium.

Table 2 Construction of the double-glazed façade

Exterior glazing	Glass: Planiclear 4 mm Saint-Gobain Glass $\tau_v = 90.5 \%$, $\rho_v = 8.2 \%$
Interior glazing	Exterior glass: Planitherm ultra N 4 mm Saint-Gobain Glass $\tau_v = 88.4 \%$, $\rho_{v1} = 4.5\%$, $\rho_{v2} = 4.8\%$
	Air gap: 16 mm air 5 %, argon 95 %
	Interior glass: Planiclear 4 mm Saint-Gobain Glass $\tau_v = 90.5 \%$, $\rho_v = 8.2 \%$

SIMPLIFIED ANNUAL GLARE EVALUATION

According the draft standard the selected location, Bratislava, belongs to sunshine zone H with 2250 annual sunshine hours. For a Southwest orientation of the daylight opening, where glazing is larger than 50 % of the façade width and the fraction of glazing area to the façade area is larger than 50 % and the upper border of the glazing is higher than 2 m above the floor, with a $\tau_{\text{glazing}} > 0.5$ the glare protection classes $DGP_{e<5\%}$ recommended for two different view directions and three distances d_w between the observer and protection device can be seen in Table 3. That means that the shading device in fully closed position with no direct transmittance and a diffuse transmittance of less than 2 % [4].

Figure 3 Venetian blinds in a closed position (left) and holes for inner cords (right).

Venetian blinds belong according the draft standard to the category of solar protection device being opaque in the extended and closed position if:

- the shading device can be operated by the occupant;
- there is no view towards sun in a fully closed position;
- the holes of inner cords of the venetian blinds are hidden;
- there is no disturbing reflection between the slats in closed position;
- there is no direct view of the sun through gaps.

The venetian blinds at the evaluated test office room are electrically operated and in a fully closed position they have a tilt of 70°. At this position they have a theoretical¹ normal/normal light transmittance $\tau_{v, n-n}$ of 0.00 and normal/diffuse light transmittance $\tau_{v, n-dif}$ of 0.002 and should therefore fulfill the requirements for glare protection class 4 [4.]. As can be seen in Figure 3 the venetian blinds at the evaluated test office room do not have hidden holes for inner cords, so an on-sight measurement would be necessary to evaluate the actual glare protection level at a fully closed position.

Table 3 Recommended glare classes according EN 14501 to fulfil glare criteria

	d_w $DGP_{e<.5\%}$	View direction parallel to the facade with a maximum viewing angle to the facade of 45°			View direction towards the facade with a viewing angle to the facade greater than 45°		
		1 m	2 m	3 m	1 m	2 m	3 m
Minimum protection	0.45	2	1	1	4	3	2
Medium protection	0.4	3	2	2	4	4	4
Maximum protection	0.35	4	4	2	4	4	4

SIMULATION BASED ANNUAL EVALUATION METHOD

To further investigate the ability of the CFS to distribute the light in the interior space illuminance distribution has been calculated for three critical days as well as the occurrence of glare was evaluated. The draft standard prEN 17037 [3.] does not define exact hours during which glare should be evaluated. The testing boundary conditions should be a clear sky condition and the sun should cause high luminance. For our simulations we have picked out the following critical days, where low sun positions might cause glare situations:

- March 21st – equinox at 12:00 PM, which corresponds to sun elevation angle of approximately 40°;
- June 21st – summer solstice at 12:00 PM, which corresponds to sun elevation angle of approximately 63°;
- December 21st – winter solstice at 12:00 PM, which corresponds to sun elevation angle of approximately 17°.

This was done for three states of the CFS:

- façade model with no blinds applied,
- façade model with blinds applied with 0° slat tilt;
- façade model with blinds with 45° slat tilt with the lower edge of the slat facing exterior.

To make the influence of the CFS on light distribution was performed for CIE clear sky model. The calculations are carried out on a plane 0.85 m above floor. The evaluation area is 4.7 × 2.0 m big whereas a band of 500 mm from the walls is excluded from the evaluation area. The grid cell size of 520 × 500 mm was used, creating a grid of 10 × 5 measurement points. Further, the glare occurrence was evaluated based on generated high dynamic range views. The observer

CFS SIMULATION

¹ acquired through virtual goniofotometry [5.]

The evaluation was performed using Radiance based computer simulation [6.]. There are different technical advances available in different simulation environments for annual simulation of CFS [7.], [8.]. In this paper a method that employs simulated bidirectional scattering distribution function (BSDF), with matrix-based annual daylighting calculations [9.]. The Radiance based 5-phase and 2-phase simulation methods were used [10.], [11.]. These follow the daylight coefficient model for dynamic simulations developed by Bourgeois et al [12.] and the Perez sky model [13.]. Here the flux transfer is broken into n-phases, independently simulated, where each phase is represented by a matrix of light transport. The concatenated flux matrices multiplied by the sky model matrix than represent the illuminance profile for each simulation point.

Figure 4 Falsecolor representation of the visible back transmission for two facade states. (The red dot represents the angle of incident flux direction).

To determine the *DGP* for the critical situations, the view direction for the test position was selected to face towards the façade parallel to the floor. The test position being 2 m from the façade in 1,2 m height. Hemispherical fish eye projections were generated and the *DGP* was calculated with the software evalglare [14.]

RESULTS

The results for illuminance distribution for the three critical days show that the façade does enable light penetration for both high and low sun elevations, Figure 5. With blinds applied with a 0°slat tilt amore even distribution of light in the office model can be achieved, while ensuring illuminance in the deep office parts.

Figure 5 Falsecolor representation of illuminance distribution (in lux) in the office model for three states of CFS. The rows correspond to CFS states, the columns to critical days. The y axis represents the façade opening of the office space.

The results from the glare simulation evaluation show that during the tested critical days, glare would not be perceived in any of the simulated situation, Table 4. This is due to the fact, that no direct source of glare is present in any of the situations. To verify our assumption we have run a simulation on a simplified model, to predict an annual occurrence of glare in for our test model and evaluation position. This was done for a calculated theoretical year with clear sky with sun. As it can be seen on Figure 6, our test critical days and critical hour of simulation, do not cover the worst-case scenarios, where sun is visible form the evaluated test position, causing intolerable glare. Further the influence of the blinds on light distribution is visible.

Table 4 Falsecolor representation of hemispherical fish eye projections for the selected testing position, critical day and CFS state

	March 21 12:00 PM	June 21 12:00 PM	December 21 12:00 PM	
Clear glass	 cd/m ² 5000 2800 1600 900 500 300 150 90 50			
	DGP = 0.33 av, L _{av} = 465.24 cd/m ²	DGP = 0.31 av, L _{av} = 333.24 cd/m ²	DGP = 0.34 av, L _{av} = 498.20 cd/m ²	
Blinds with 0° tilt slats				
	DGP = 0.30 av, L _{av} = 341.83 cd/m ²	DGP = 0.29 av, L _{av} = 263.37 cd/m ²	DGP = 0.32 av, L _{av} = 449.33 cd/m ²	
Blinds with 45° tilt slats				
	DGP = 0.22 av, L _{av} = 139.79 cd/m ²	DGP = 0.22 av, L _{av} = 139.86 cd/m ²	DGP = 0.23 av, L _{av} = 135.69 cd/m ²	

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this article a simulation method based on flux transmission of complex fenestration system for the purpose to evaluate the ability of the CFS to distribute the light in the interior space and to prevent glare, illuminance distribution in the office space. The results have shown that for glare evaluation, the use of usual critical days such as equinox, summer and winter solstice might not be representative for the evaluation of glare occurrence. It is recommended to create a predictive model of annual glare occurrence, for a theoretical year model with clear sky with sun, according to which the test critical situations will be selected.

Figure 6 Prediction of annual glare occurrence for a simplified model, for a theoretical year model with clear sky with sun.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was carried out in the framework of the „Papabuild“ project under the action H2020-MSCA-RISE-2015 – grant 690970.

REFERENCES

- [1.] IESNA. *The IESNA Lighting handbook* [online]. 9th editio. New York : IESNA, 2000. ISBN 0-87-995-150-8. Available from: Rea, Mark V.
- [2.] CIE. *International lighting vocabulary* [online]. 2011. CIE S 017:2011. Available from: <http://eilv.cie.co.at/>
- [3.] prEN 17037 (2017) *Daylight of buildings*.
- [4.] EN 14501 (2005) *Blinds and shutters - Thermal and visual comfort - Performance characteristics and classification*.
- [5.] Mitchel, R. *et al.* (2013) *THERM 6.3 / WINDOW 6.3. NFRC Simulation Manual*. Berkeley. Available at: <https://windows.lbl.gov/software/NFRC/SimMan/NFRCsim6.3-2013-07-Manual.pdf>.
- [6.] Ward, G. J. (2014) *The RADIANCE 4.2 Synthetic Imaging System*. Berkeley. Available at: <http://radsite.lbl.gov/radiance/refer/ray.html#Font>.
- [7.] Fitz, A. (2006) ‘Findings from a survey on the current use of daylight simulations in building design’, *Energy and Buildings*, 38(7), pp. 824–835. doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2006.03.012.
- [8.] Brembilla, E. (2016) ‘Survey on Climate-Based Daylight Modelling workflows’, in *15th International Radiance Workshop Padova, 29-31 August 2016*. Padova, p. 27. Available at: <https://www.radiance-online.org/community/workshops/2016-padua/presentations/204-Brembilla-CBDMsurvey.pdf>.
- [9.] Saxena, M. *et al.* (2010) ‘Dynamic Radiance - Predicting Annual Daylighting with Variable Fenestration Optics Using BSDFs’, in *Fourth National Conference of IBPSA-USA*. New York, pp. 402–409. Available at: <https://www.ibpsa.us/sites/default/files/publications/SB10-DOC-TS08A-01-Saxena.pdf>.
- [10.] McNeil, A. (2013) *The Five-Phase Method for Simulating Complex Fenestration with Radiance*. Berkeley.
- [11.] McNeil, A. (2014) *The Three Phase Method for Simulating Complex Fenestration with Radiance*. Available at: <https://www.radiance-online.org/learning/tutorials/Tutorial-ThreePhaseMethod.pdf>.
- [12.] Burgeois, D., Reinhart, C. F. and Ward, G. J. (2008) ‘Standard daylight coefficient model for dynamic daylighting simulations’, *Building Research & Information*, 36(1), pp. 68–82. doi: 10.1080/09613210701446325.
- [13.] Igawa, N. *et al.* (2004) ‘Models of sky radiance distribution and sky luminance distribution’, *Solar Energy*, 77(2), pp. 137–157. doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2004.04.016.
- [14.] Brotas, L. and Wienold, J. (2014) ‘Solar reflected glare’, in *13th International Radiance Workshop*. London, p. 66. Available at: https://www.radiance-online.org/community/workshops/2014-london/presentations/day3/Brotas_SolarReflectedGlare.pdf.